

Review Article

A Critical Analysis of the Concept of Trust Under the Nigerian Jurisprudence

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Abstract

Until recently, individual title of land holding was very rare because it is a practice that was hardly known to customary law and it was usually held as repugnant to the natural phenomena as we have it among us in Nigeria. But all that had changed and we now have the concept of trust in real property administration. Since the main element of trust is that a particular property is vested in a trustee for the benefit of the beneficiary, the trustee being the legal owner who manage and safeguard the trust property in a productive manner. This article explores and examined the concept of trust as it affects the administration of real property. It also looked into the massive growth of commerce and industry, complex business transactions arising from the growth, the problems inherent in these evolving commercial relationships, with emphasis on the practicality of the trust concept in these commercial relationships. Similarly, the legal assertion that, constructive trust is a vital legal mechanism through which the conscience of equity finds expression was examined. Situation arises when real property is acquired in such circumstances that the legal title holder may not in good conscience keep the beneficial interest, equity will make him a trustee of the property. Hence, this work assessed the degree to which constructive trust as equitable remedy is applicable under the Nigeria legal system. Information was gathered and collected through secondary data collection method. It was found in the course of this work that the concept of trust had brought about a positive revolution into the Nigerian jurisprudence. Yet, more still need to be done to consolidate on the benefits derived from the trust concept.

Keywords: Nigeria legal system, land holding, jurisprudence, trust concept, trustee, property

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Introduction

The origin of the legal concept of trust in Nigeria cannot be fully discussed except with an extensive inquiry into the evolution of its history. The exact origin of trust cannot be ascertained and there are controversies surrounding the subject. However, it is certain that the Chancery Court entertained trust cases at a point in time. One school of thought believed that trust was transplanted into England from the Roman Legal System. Another school of thought however disproved that English law of trust has no any connection with Roman laws. Notwithstanding this controversy, the law of trusts as we now have in England was greatly influenced by the Chancellors in the Chancery Courts which administered equity, in their enforcement of 'uses'.

The origin of the modern concept of trust has been credited to the concept of *uses* during the medieval period, which was a means of conveying land to someone for the use of one or more persons. The concept then was that a person called the 'feofor' conveyed land to another person called the 'feofee' for the benefit of one person or more called the beneficiaries'. The Common law of England recognizes only the feoffee as the one who holds the legal title to the property so conveyed, without taken any cognizance of the interest of the beneficiary. Hence, it is common for the feoffee to put to use such property for his sole benefit instead of that of the beneficiary. Similarly, the feoffee usually treats the property in an unconscionable way to the detriment of the beneficiary and in some extreme cases the feoffee may retain such property for himself and the beneficiary will not be able to get relief or remedy from the Common Law Courts.

The concept of *trust* was first introduced into the Nigeria Jurisprudence by the Statute of General Application of 1st January 1900, which made it mandatory that all Laws in operation in England be applicable in Nigeria and all other British Colonies. The subsequent Legislations and Ordinances in force during the colonial era, also had its fair share of influence on the Concept of trust in Nigeria. It is of utmost importance to note however that, several case laws, local laws, customs and traditions also contributed immensely to the concept of trust in Nigeria.

It has to be noted here that, the concept of family ownership of land in Nigeria served a purpose similar to that of trust, where the concept of individual ownership is a foreign one, rather, land belongs to the family and the head of family holds the family land for the use of the family members. The head of family to some extent assumes the position of a trustee and all members of the family have equal right to the property. See *Amodu Tijani v. Secretary of Southern Nigeria* [1921] 1A.C. 399 at p. 404¹ per Lord Haldane. The

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concept of trust under customary law is however different from that under the English law because while the trustee is regarded as the owner of the trust property, the head of family is not regarded as the owner of the family property, but rather as the caretaker.

The Land Use Act also embodied the concept of trust by vesting the control and management of land in each State of the Federation in the governors to be held in trust and administered for the use and common benefit of all Nigerians. See the Supreme Court decision in *Abioye v. Yakubu* [1991] 5 NWLR (Pt. 190) p. 130

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Although the concept of trust under the Land Use Act is not the same as in the law of trusts for the mere fact that, the trustee under the Act, which is the Governor cannot be compelled to render account as trustee under English law. But a special kind of trust is created under the Act, known and regarded as a bare trust.

Background of Study

One may be forced to argue that the reception of the English law of trust in Nigeria is to complement the existing trust rules in Nigeria. It is of importance to note that, prior to the partition of Africa and the subsequent imposition of the British legal regime on Nigeria, the idea of trust was inherent in our culture, customs and traditions. One may even be tempted to argue that the British benefited from the Nigerian concept of trust. For example, individual ownership of land was alien to our native ideas. Land was usually believed to be a Communal or Family property and as such not an individual property. It was generally accepted that the totality of the Community or family as the case may be, have equal right and access to a particular Communal or Family land. The Chief or head of the Community, Village or Family are those that have charge over such lands. They may be loosely referred to as the land owners, but in reality they only hold the title as a trustee for the benefits of individual component of the Community, Village or Family.

Statement of the Problem

There is a tremendous need for the overview of the application of the concept of trust under the Nigeria Jurisprudence. Until recently, the application of the trust concept in the Nigeria legal system was to a minimal extent. There were only very few cases where it was applied. It is on note that trust, if embraced and applied effectively will go a long way in solving issues arising from land and other intangible properties, as well as, commercial relationship. To achieve the above, there is need to educate the greater populace of Nigeria the inherent benefits of the trust concept.

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Objective of Study

Trust is a foreign concept of law, and like other received English laws has failed to yield much result in Nigeria due to the fact that those laws are built on English ideals which are not compatible with our own ideals, culture, customs and traditions. In the view of the above, this work is aim at elucidating more on the concept of *trust* in the Nigerian context. It will also look into the duties and power of trustees and how these responsibilities can be undertaken without prejudicing the interest of the beneficiaries of a trust. There is no gain saying otherwise, research has shown that some of the trustees usually violate the terms of trust by acting outside the limits of their trusteeship, thereby failing to carry out their essential *duty of care* which by extension leads to the breach of the trust. Suggestions on how to mitigate the above scenario will be provided for in this work.

Review Questions

This essay seeks to provide answers as to:

1. What is the relationship between trust and customary land tenure system in Nigeria?
2. How successful was the application of customary law and received trust law in Nigeria?
3. How effective is the application of the concept of trust in commercial relationships compared to family relationship which trust were primarily used for?
4. Is constructive trust a vital legal mechanism through which the conscience of equity finds expression?

Methodology

The use of secondary data is the primary method of approach employed in this essay, this include but not limited to textbooks written by renowned authors and scholars whom had been certified as expert and authority in the field of law and any other legal related field. In a similar vein, the various judicial decisions of Nigerian courts on issues of trust and local statutes will be put to use and explore to get a grasp of the Nigeria's content of trust.

Trust and Nigerian Customary Land Tenure

Under Customary law, title or ownership to land ranges from individual, Communal, to family ownership. The term ownership is a multi-referential word, which does not lend itself to an apt or precise definition. The issue becomes more complex when the word is to be defined in the context of customary land law. The ordinary meaning of ownership

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is defined as collection of rights to use and enjoy property, including right to transmit it to others. It is the complete dominion, title to proprietary right in a thing or claim³. It means the entirety of the powers of use and disposal allowed by law. It is the right of one or more persons to possess and use a thing to the exclusion of others. It is the right by which a thing belongs to someone in particular, to the exclusion of all other persons.

It means the exclusive right of possession, enjoyment, and disposal involving as an essential attribute the right to control, handle and disposal⁴. Black's Law Dictionary defines ownership to mean the collection of rights allowing one to use and enjoy property, including the right to convey it to others. Ownership implies the right to possess a thing, regardless of any actual or constructive control. Nwabueze explained the concept of ownership "as the most comprehensive and complete relation that can exist in respect of anything. It implies the fullest amplitude of rights of enjoyment, management and disposal over property. Put differently, it implies that the owner's title to these rights is superior and paramount over any other rights that may exist in the land in favour of other persons"⁵.

The next issue for determination is that of ownership of land under customary law. In other word, who owns land under customary law? This has been succinctly stated in the celebrated case of *Amodu Tijani v Secretary of Southern Nigeria* [1921] C399 at 404⁶. In this case, the appellant was one of the Idejo white cap chiefs of Lagos. He was the head Chief of the Oluwa family or community and one of the Idejos or land owing white cap Chiefs of Lagos and the land in question was situated at Apapa and was occupied by persons some of whom paid rent or tribute to him. By a notice dated November 12, 1913 certain lands situated at Apapa were acquired by the Government of the Colony under the Public Lands Ordinance (No. 5 of 1903) for public purposes.

The essential character of customary land law is that land belongs to the community, the village or the family. Individual ownership of land is a foreign concept. Under customary law, all members of the community, village or family have an equal right to the land. Title to land is vested in the corporate unit. Individuals cannot lay claim to any portion of it as the owner. Individual rights are limited to the use and enjoyment of the land. The community head is a caretaker performing administrative functions in a representative capacity and does not have sole rights in the land⁷.

The Chief or administrator of the village or head of family has charge of the land and is only loosely called the owner. He is in essence a trustee and as such holds the land in trust for the use of the community or family. Every member who wants to use it is entitled

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to be allocated an adequate piece for cultivation to satisfy his/her needs but cannot dispose of such land without the consent of the elders of the community⁸. This legal status of land is in no way affected by the super-imposed statutory regime of the colonial administration through the Crowns Land Act. The only meaning of such super-imposition was to vest the root title to land in the Crown but only notionally as actual ownership was retained by the community and the individuals who worked the land. In effect the individual once allocated land enjoys all attributes of “owner” and in case of eminent domain, compensation paid goes to him/her.

The concept of trusteeship is well founded in the system of ownership under customary law e.g. ownership of family property under customary law is vested in the family as a unit but the power of management and control of such property is vested in the head of the family and he is strictly enjoined to exercise the power for the benefit of himself as well as other members of the family⁹. He enjoys a wide discretion in the exercise of his power as long as he discharges his duties in accordance with rules of customary law. Due to the managerial duties of the family head, he is often referred to as the owner of family property but in the real sense of it, he acts somewhat as a trustee, holding family property on behalf of the family members who would be regarded as the beneficiaries. However, the concept of family property under customary law maintains a strict distinction between management and the beneficial enjoyment of family property.

The Application of Customary Law and Received Trust Law in Nigeria

There are three (3) types of land title under native law and custom, namely, communal title, family title, and individual title.

Individual Title

It was very rare in the past to hear of Individual title or land holding it is a practice that was hardly known to customary law. This was looked upon as being repugnant to natural phenomena among Nigerians¹⁰. The only systems of land-holding known to the people there communal and family holding. This indeed, was the gradual development of Individual land holding¹¹. This process was accelerated when other reasons which favoured individual ownership of land increased or multiplied¹². The main reasons for the fragmentation of the family system of land holding to an individual system were the social and economic development, the growth of education and health services, the introduction of a money economy and the modernization living standards¹³.

Individual tenure is a feature of land holding that is now known throughout Nigeria. Thus. it would seem that the basis of concept of family property is the recognition of

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individual ownership, for when founder of a family who acquired land dies, his- self acquired property devolves on his children as family property as there was no notion of sale or device of land¹⁴.

From the foregoing, it is abundantly clear that authorities have firmly established the existence of individual tenure as a feature of customary land law and the individual acts as a trustee for the beneficiaries in respect of the land. This is so because as soon as he dies the interest in the land reverts to the family as the land for re-allotment to other members of the family. This is how the trust law comes into play under customary land law.

Communal Title

The word "communal" means a group of people. This group of people may be a tribe, a town, a village or an extended family. The group may speak the same language, share the same culture, and form a distinct social and political entity. It may also be a single autonomous unit or a parent village with a number of off- shoots¹⁵. Another kind of a community is that which is free from all kinship factors and based solely on geographical contiguity, common residence on the same soil serving to bind its heterogeneous elements into a single society in which every individual has an equal claim to a share of the common land for cultivation, building and graving¹⁶. In a community, land is held by an individual and is expressed to be vested in the head. The rights are exercised through headmen of villages and ward- heads who may be hereditary or appointive offices who distribute land to those who need it, control the common pastures and supervise the admission of non-member-strangers¹⁷. The concept of communal land means that individual members of a political or social group have certain claims, powers, privileges and immunities in or over the land vis-à-vis the political authorities or other members of the group.

In this sense the land belongs to the community and the word is use as a description of a group which considers itself, and is regarded in law or by the society, as a corporate entity. Communal land holding is largely practiced throughout Nigeria. The whole of the village land belongs to the village community at large. The principle involved is that every member of the community is entitled to the use and enjoyment of the land. The village or the community chief and his councillors manage and control the land for the common benefit of the people. Every member of the community has an inalienable right of access to the community land. The community rights extend to declaring some parcels of land for public use such as road construction, markets, meeting places, burial and sacred lands and grazing land. Where compensation is paid for the community land by

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the government, the payment goes for the use and benefit of the whole community¹⁸. The same can be said of money collected from lease, loan or sale of the community land. The community has the reversionary right in cases of abandonment and revocation of grants to strangers¹⁹.

The control and management of communal land is vested in the chief and his councillors who are the trustees of the community land hence the relevance of trust law to the community land. Although the chief is the chief executive with regard to control, his work is normally done by the ward heads. The ward-head allots land to members of the community freely without consulting the chief. However, the chief must be consulted where the grant is to a total stranger. The chief or ward-head may be called the “land lord”²⁰. It should however, be stressed at this point that the word landlord here does not have the same meaning as the word landlord or tenant under the English Law. While the landlord in the latter is the proprietary owner of the land and has exclusive control and rights in the land, the former is only a trustee²¹ and a representative of the community from whom he derives his powers over land. The authority of the chief over land is derived from: (a) His being the trustee of the community land²² and (b) his being the legal representative of the community⁴⁵.

Family Title

The family system of land ownership is a system whereby the whole family holds land jointly. They may use the land jointly or separately, but the ultimate ownership of the land lies in the whole family. One may rightly observe that family land-holding represents one of the main forms of land-holding in Nigeria. The ownership of the family land lies in the family as a corporate entity. The legal power to control and manage land lays in the family as a unit. This, therefore, means that all the family members have the rights and liabilities in the land. Thus, the holding of family land under customary law is joint and indivisible²³ unless partition takes place. In fact, even when partition is said to have taken place upon the death of the individual owner his interest reverts back to his family and it thereby continues as the family property. The head of the family will in this regard be seen as a trustee²⁴ of the family land and this make his activities come under the trust law. Hence, relevance of trust law in administration of real property under customary law.

A head of family is the person who manages family property for and on behalf of other family members. The head of the family represents the family at any gathering or

⁴⁵ *Ibid*

occasion. He is the family voice at the village or community meeting²⁵. He is the trustee of the family property²⁶. He is accountable to the family members as to how he manages the family property²⁷ and every other thing in respect of the family property²⁸. He must relate to the family the decision of the village or community meetings, when family property is sold he must account to the family members²⁹. The family head can be appointed by operation of law or expressly.

Appointment of Family Head by the Founder

The founder of family property has always been able to appoint a head of his own choice, with an unlimited and uncontrolled discretion in his choice, to the point of even selecting a stranger. As to what will be the position of the stranger who is appointed as the family head the case of *Sogbesan v Adebiyi* [1941] 6 N.L.R 26 at p.27³⁰ provide the answer by suggesting that if a person who is not a member of the family is appointed head, he is deemed to be included in the family with rights and duties as the natural members. In that case, the testator appointed a brother to be the head of his (the deceased's) family and directed that he should act in all family matters under the direction, control and advice of the testator's mother and aunt. The appointment was held valid.

Apart from any such express appointment however, younger brothers of deceased heads of families usually succeeded to the family headship under the ancient and, it would seem, many modern systems of land tenure³¹. In *Ajoke v Olateju* [1962] LLR 32³² the plaintiff, Ajoke was one of the descendants of one Buko who was the original owner of the family property at Surulere and the founder of the Buko family of which she was also the oldest living member. Mustafa the head of the family who died immediately before the institution of these proceedings had purported on his death-bed to appoint the defendant, Olateju, as the head of the family on the incorrect ground that no other relative of his was still alive, and also to authorise her to collect the rents from the property.

The plaintiff sued for a declaration that she was the family head, for accounts and for injunction restraining the defendant from collecting any more rents or otherwise dealing with the property. The plaintiff was a grand-daughter of Buko, but the defendant was not in the direct line. It was held that the plaintiff succeeded because, although the original founder of the family and owner of the property is entitled to make a death bed disposition of his property even so as to displace a person who would otherwise be entitled under customary law, a subsequent family head is not so entitled. There is no restriction on a female being appointed the head by the founder of the family³³.

Appointment of Family Head by Members of the Family

This will arise when the family head lost the support of his family members. In this regard, the family members may resolve to remove such head and appoint another in his place. Or, when there is a vacancy the family may look for a person they believe is best suited to hold the office and appoint him. There can be no doubt that female member may be elected by popular vote in this way³⁴.

Rights and Duties of the Head of Family as a Trustee

Rights according to Black's Law Dictionary means "a power, privilege, faculty or demand inherent in one person and incident upon another rights as generally defined as power of free action". The head of the family is also a member of the family and whatever right is due to any member of the family is equally due to the head of the family. It is on this note and to avoid repetition, it will be neater and more convenient to treat the rights of the head of the family jointly with that of the members of the family. Thus, the general management and control of the family property is in the hands of the family head³⁵. He is the proper person to look after the property. He keeps documents of title (if any) and other documents relating to the land. He also negotiates transactions affecting the land on behalf of the family. However, the consent of the family is required before he can dispose of family property. It is within his power to allocate portions of the family land or rooms in the house to members or strangers⁴⁶. He does not require the consent of the family in order to exercise his discretion and unless it is misused, for example by treating the family property as his only property. It should be stressed here that the right of management vested in the head of family is a trust, which he must exercise in accordance with trust law.

In many cases, the duties of the head of the family are similar to those of a chief. Thus he is a trustee and beneficiary of the family land³⁶. In *Bassey v Cobham* [1924] 5 N.L.R 90 and others, it was held that the head of the family in possession of family land is analogous to that of a trustee, and the members of the family being beneficiaries, any member may claim his duties, in respect of the family communal land, if the head neglects or refuses to assert such rights. The Head of family allocates family land to other members and where there is surplus he makes grants to strangers after consultation with the elders of the family⁴⁷. Actions affecting family land are brought by the head as a legal representative of the family. In *Aregbe v Adeoye & Anor* [1974] 5 NLR 90, the action was brought by the family heads of Eweino Court a compound in Lagos, praying that the

⁴⁶ *Lewis v. Bankole* [1909] 1 NLR 82

⁴⁷ [1924] 5 N.L.R 90

defendants be restrained from building houses on an adjacent piece of land over which they had hitherto exercised by local law and custom such a degree of control as to entitle their families as owners and occupiers of the houses in the compound to use and enjoyment of the surrounding open space³⁷.

The head men could under customary law grant permission to other people to occupy temporarily part of this open space, and they did permit one Labinjoh to erect a shed on part thereof since such a structure interfered little with their use and enjoyment of the land. But the plaintiffs in the instant case were non-suited by the Supreme Court overriding the Divisional Court, because instead of basing their claim on local law and custom they had claimed a prescriptive right of user - a concept of English law. Any member of the family may however, institute an action in the court to protect the family where the head is absent or has decided to keep quiet. The head's routine and emergency actions in good faith bind the other members. Where it is not done in good faith, the head is personally responsible for his action³⁸. In the case of *Fako v Fako* [1965] NMLR 3 the defendant, who was the head of Fako family, sold three houses belonging to the family with the consent of only one member.

The head of the family has a duty to keep accounts and the information available to other members. They had managed the property for the family in accordance with usual custom which did not require the keeping of accounts. It was held that in the circumstances the plaintiff was not entitled to claim an account as of right and that his claim for an account must be dismissed. Under the traditional practice, the head of the family was not accountable to other members of the family as to how he manages the family property. This was the position then, because in those days the needs of the society were very limited. The desire to hold property individually was rarely heard of. The paramount consideration of the head of the family was the smooth running of the family's affairs not much concern was given to property.

Rights and Duties of Family Members as Beneficiaries under Customary Trust

Every member of family as a beneficiary has some inalienable right in the family property under customary trust. Every member of the family including the head of the family has the right to reside on the family property³⁹. This right basically includes use and enjoyment of the family property. This right springs from unity of possession, which exists from the nature of the title held by the family⁴⁰. In a situation where the house is too small for the family or a portion has been let out, it cannot be occupied by all the members, in such cases, the right of possession will be represented by the right to share in the rents and profit derived there from. The position of the female members to reside

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in the family property is the same as that of their male counterpart. The only difference is that the males can leave with their wives and children⁴¹ while in the case of the females the moment they marry, they do not have the right to bring their husbands on to the premises to reside with her and her husband has no interest in the property⁴².

The issue that may come to mind at this point would be that of discrimination. By not allowing the female to bring in her family into the family property like her brother, it amounts to discrimination. It is the opinion of this writer that as long as anybody is a family member his or her right should not be short changed by virtue of his/her gender. If the female member decides to bring her family onto her family property she should be allowed to do so. After all, they have equal right in the property. Above all, she did not choose her own sex, nor did anybody determine her sex. The next issue for determination is what will be the position if the family property is shared out?

This is no more than the right to be consulted as a family member before any important dealing with the family property is carried out and the right of members to be presented through their branches on the family council. The right of consultation is however, limited in respect of the persons to be consulted, and the occasion when consultation is necessary. The principal members of the family are to be consulted when alienation or sale takes place⁴³. However, every member of the family enjoys that right of being informed about any dealings in respect of the family property. This way they express their views in the management of the family property.

Income or profit, whether in the form of rents, proceeds of sale, lease or compensation for compulsory acquisition by any governments, individual or corporate body that is realized from the family land, belongs to all the members of the family⁴⁴ and for this purpose a member is entitled to a share. The share of a member may be in money or in kind. It all depends on what is given out as compensation.

Village head as a trustee

A village head is a trustee of the community land. He administers land for the use and common benefit of the people. He cannot sell or make an outright gift of community land. By the village head being a trustee of the community land, means that he represents his community in all dealings related to the community land, and this of course, includes, any dispute in respect of the community land. Thus, he can sue and can be sued for any matter connected with the community land⁴⁵. As a trustee the village head has to act in accordance with what is expected of a trustee that is, he has to act in good faith, he has to be accountable to the community *inter alia*⁴⁶.

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Rights and duties of Community Members as Beneficiaries

The community members being the beneficiary of communal land, have some in a liable rights and duties owed them by the village head as the trustee of the communal land.

Right to be Informed and Consulted: As pointed out above, the village head can sell communal land. If the need arises for sale of communal land, it is a matter of right for the community members to be informed of such sale. It is also a matter of right for community (members) to be consulted when major decisions in respect of communal land has to be taken. It may include alienation of communal land by the village head.

The Right of Allocation: The administrative and management control of communal land is vested in the village head who exercises it on behalf of members of the community. Every member has a right in conjunction with others in the use and enjoyment of Communal land. This right is an inherent right vested on every member of the family by virtue of his membership and can be enforced against the village head in the court⁴⁷.

Duty to be Respectful and Obey the Laws of the Land: The community owes respect to the village head who is the trustee of the community. Without being respectful to the village head, he will find it virtually impracticable to discharge his responsibilities as a trustee. The foregoing are the rights and duties of community members under a communal trust.

FORMALITIES IN CREATION OF TRUST

No formality is required for the creation of a trust if the property involved is in personalities, i.e. tangible personal movable properties, such as vehicles, shoes, television, etc. including money. What is essential is that, the manifestation of the intention to create a trust on the part of the settlor must be very clear, such is the case in *Paul v. Constance* [1977] WLR 521⁴⁸. Mere intention to benefit an imprecise person will not be sufficient, *Jones v. Lock* [1865] L.R. 1 Ch. App. 25⁴⁹.

If the property is realty (i.e. immovable property, such as land), the intention to benefit someone must be evidenced in writing as required by the Statute of Frauds, Section 7; which requires that any declaration of trust relating to land to be evidenced by a memorandum in writing signed by the party creating the trust. The position on the States forming the old Western Nigeria is captured by Section 78(1)(b) of the Property and

⁴⁸ [1977] WLR 521

⁴⁹ [1865] L.R. 1 Ch. App. 25

Conveyancing Law, which provides to the same effect that any declaration in trust in respect of land or any interest therein must be evidenced and proved by some writing signed by some person who is able to declare such trust or by his will. See *Forster v. Hale* [1798] 3 Ves 696 per Arden M.R.⁵⁰.

One must know that failure to comply with the above formalities may be fatal as the trust will be rendered unenforceable. Also note that, writing is not required in respect of constructive and resulting trusts in realty since these are implied and arise independently of the exercise of the will of the parties.

In order to create a trust by will, some formalities are required both for the validity of the will and of the trust. According to the law, (The Will's Act 1837 Section 9 as amended by the Wills Amendment Act 1957 and the Wills Law 1959 Cap. 133 Laws of Western Nigeria 1959 applicable to the States forming the old Western Nigeria), requirements to create a trust by will are:

- i. The will must be in writing⁵¹.
- ii. It must be signed by the testator or by some other person in his presence and by his direction.
- iii. The signature of the testator must be attested by two witnesses, who must be present together in the presence of the testator⁵².

Failure to comply with the above provisions of the law will render the trust to be void and no interest will pass under the will. Exceptions to this are secret trusts, whereby irrespective of the non-compliance with the provisions of the law, dispositions made under such trusts can be enforced in equity. In order to create a valid express trust, part of the requirements is the legal capacity of the settlor, whether individual, corporation or statutory bodies, to create it. Related to this is the capacity of a person to hold interest in real property. Where a person cannot hold interest in land, this will affect the capacity to create a trust. The situation of capacity to hold interest in land varies according to the operative law. The issues will now be examined as follows:

Capacity to Create Trust

At common law for instance, an infant is capable of holding a legal interest in landed property. However, a sale or disposition of such property is voidable and may be repudiated before the infant attains the age of majority or within a reasonable time after

⁵⁰ [1798] 3 Ves 696 per Arden M.R

⁵¹ *Ibid* Law of Property Act 1925

⁵² Section 9 Wills Act 1837

attaining the age of majority. At common law, 21 years was adopted as the age of majority and anyone below this age is an infant. Thus, the position of an infant or a minor who attempts to create a trust, especially in a situation where the trust is not in his interest, will have the same effect at common law.

Individual

In common law, age of majority is 21 years and this position has been restated by some State laws in the Federation, example is Section 2 of the Infants Law, Cap. 49 Laws of Western Region which states that, an infant is someone under the age of twenty-one years⁵³. This has been adopted and now applicable in States forming the old Western Region of Nigeria. Consequently, any person of 21 years of age and above is regarded as of full age and has the capacity to hold legal interest in real property. Although, some statutory provisions have specified 18 years as “age of majority” or “full age”, for example, section 277 of the Child’s Right Act, Sections 29 (4)(a) and 35(1)(d) of the 1999 Constitution, and Section 20(1)(a) of the Companies and Allied Matters Act. The age of majority in Nigeria for other purposes nevertheless remains 21 years. This was the position of the Court of Appeal in *Elias v Elias* [2001] 9 N.W.L.R. (Part 718) p. 429⁵⁴.

With respect to the States where the Settled Act, 1882 operates in Nigeria, and an infant has interest in a real property, such land becomes a settled land. Thus, the infant becomes a tenant for life and the statutory powers vested in the infant as tenant for life will be exercised on his behalf by the trustees of that settlement⁵⁵. It follows from the above that an infant cannot create a trust of real property or create a valid will except such an infant is a soldier at war or mariners at sea. An infant can however create a trust over both legal and equitable interest in pure personality and over equitable interest only in real property.

People with Mental Disability

People with mental disability also cannot validly create or have a trust enforced directly against them since their mental deficiency may itself encumber their ability to validly dispose their properties or make will. Some of the things that may invalidate such trusts are the possible contradicting instructions of the insane settlor/testator or that he/she does not appreciate the nature or effect of such instructions as seen in *Re Beaney* [1978] 1 W.L.R. 770⁵⁶. It is however possible to approach the courts for directions in respect of

⁵³ Section 2, Infant Act CAP. 49 Laws of Western Region

⁵⁴ [2001] 9 N.W.L.R. (Part 718) p. 429

⁵⁵ Settled Act 1882

⁵⁶ [1978] 1 W.L.R. 770

the settlement to be made on the property of an insane person. For example, Section 180 of the Property and Conveyancing Law and Section make provisions as to how to deal with such property. If the trust was created during the time that such an insane settlor was in his lucid period and he/she fully understands the nature of his act and the consequences of the same, such trust may be upheld as valid⁵⁷.

Statutory and Incorporated Companies

Statutory bodies and incorporated companies can also create trusts if the power to do so is contained in their enabling law and memorandum of association, otherwise any trust created will be declared ultra vires. By virtue of Section 38(1) of the Companies and Allied Matters Act, incorporated companies have all the powers of a natural person of full age and capacity in the execution of its business and objects. In effect, they can create trusts without such powers being expressly contained in their memo, the power to do so may be limited by their memorandum of association or by law⁵⁸.

Application of the Concept of Trust in Institutions, Constructive Trust and Case Law in Nigeria

For centuries, trusts were primarily used in family relationships. The instrument of trust was a safe haven for fathers who sought to secure family wealth for their children who could not at the time due to obvious incapacities be vested with title to the property. The need to provide property for mistresses, illegitimate children, pursue educational, charitable and religious purposes was one of the chief motives behind the use of trust. Security of testamentary property, faithful distribution and accountability of the trustee were added attractions to its continued importance and increasing popularity in the family. However, with the massive growth of commerce and industry, complex business transactions arose. These commercial relationships, as was bound to be, posed their own peculiar problems. There then arises the dire need for protection of hugely contrasting commercial interests. Happily, the equitable trust, once again, provided the solution. It was developed beyond its previous family boundaries to accommodate commercial relations⁵⁹. Some rules like those relating to investment and delegation were perfectly suited to the commercial world and became guidelines for the administration of financial and economic related trusts. Interestingly, in the different spheres of commerce, one of

⁵⁷ Section 180, Property and Conveyance Law CAP. 100 Laws of Western Region of Nigeria

⁵⁸ Section 38(i) CAMA 2004

⁵⁹ Security and Exchange Commission Rules and Regulations 2002, 2003, 2005 for its regulation on collective investment schemes through trust, particularly unit trusts.

the areas which warmly embraced the application of trust principles was retirement benefit schemes otherwise known as pension schemes⁶⁰.

Trust and Pension Scheme

For a trust to be validly created, certain property must vest in a person known as a trustee who holds it for the benefit of another or in some cases for his own benefit. The trustee's title, having been validly vested by law, is usually legal while that of the beneficiary is, consequently, equitable and the property so vested may be personal, real or tangible.

A pension trust is a type of trust through which pension funds are vested in a trustee or trustees for the benefit of an employee under a pension scheme. Pension, however, is a periodic payment made by a government or private organization, by virtue of a fund etc. to an employee, whether private or public, on retirement or on the attainment of a specific age in order to take care of his needs after retirement and as a reward for his service. It has been defined by the Court of Appeal as "a contract for a fixed sum to be paid regularly by installments on retirement from service"⁶¹ and as "an accrued right of an employee, be it the right in money or other consideration, on retiring from the services of his employer and satisfying the conditions for payment of the said pension"⁶².

Pension trusts are occupational in nature; that is, they revolve around the relations between an employer and an employee, with the employee as the beneficiary and, in traditional common law pension trusts, the employer as the settlor⁶³. Pension trusts came into use for the protection of pension scheme at the beginning of the 20th Century. In 1921, trust became the basis for safeguarding private occupational pension schemes because of the introduction of tax relief. After the Second World War, pension trusts became firmly established and is widely used in England, Canada, Australia etc⁶⁴. The traditional pension trust was created by the employer setting up a pension scheme and vesting the title of any contributions made by him or both him and the employee in the trustee through a trust deed. The trustee was responsible for the administration and management of the trust in line with the terms of the trust and contract of employment. The pension trust was suitable for both the defined benefit scheme, where the employer contributed all the money and the contributory scheme where both the employer and employee contributed.

⁶⁰ Moffat, G. (2005). *Trusts Law, Text and Materials*. 4th ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press).

⁶¹ Kasim v. NNPC [2013] 10 NWLR (Pt 1361) pg. 69, para C-D.

⁶² Momodu v. National Union of Local Government Employees [1994] 8 NWLR (pt 362) pg. 336.

⁶³ Moffat, G. (2005). *Trusts Law, Text and Materials*. 4th ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press). Pg. 670.

⁶⁴ Moffat, G., op. cit. pg. 645

The Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2014 establishes a contributory pension scheme for payment of retirement benefit of employees to everyone the scheme applies to⁶⁵. The scheme involves the creation of a retirement savings account in the name of the employee in which contributions to the pension fund created by the Act will be credited⁶⁶. The contributions will be made by both the employer and employee. The Act defines a retirement savings account as “an account opened with a pension fund administrator...⁶⁷” while a pension fund is defined as “an investment fund within the pension scheme which is intended to accumulate during an individual’s working life from contributions and investment income, with the intention of providing income in retirement from the purchase of an annuity or in the form of a programmed withdrawal, with the possible option of an additional tax free cash lump sum being paid to the individual”

The pension fund administrator (PFA) where the retirement savings account is domicile in the manager of the fund while a pension fund custodian (PFC) established by the Act keeps custody of the pension fund. The contribution of the employer and employee is a minimum of ten percent and a minimum of eight per cent, respectively, of the employees’ monthly emoluments. An employee who operates the contributory pension scheme shall, upon retirement or attaining the age of 50 years, whichever is later, utilize the amount credited to his retirement savings account for:

- i. a withdrawal of a lump sum from the total amount credited to his retirement savings account provided that the amount left after the lump sum withdrawal shall be sufficient to procure a programme fund withdrawal or annuity⁶⁸ for life in accordance with extant guidelines issued by the commission, from time to time
- ii. programmed monthly or quarterly withdrawals calculated on the basis of an expected life span,
- iii. annuity for life purchased from a life insurance company licensed by the national insurance commission with monthly or quarterly payments in line with guidelines jointly issued by the commission and national insurance commission⁶⁹.

⁶⁵ Section 3(i) of the Pension Reform Act 2014

⁶⁶ *Ibid* Section 11(i)

⁶⁷ *Ibid* Section 120

⁶⁸ Section 120 of the Pension Reform Act 2014

⁶⁹ *Ibid* Section 7(i)(a)-(c)

It will be no surprise if the question as to whether the Pension Reform Act has created a pension trust in favour of employees is answered in the negative. For the Act⁷⁰ seems to give passing reference to the concept of trust and neglect the importance of a trust to the contributory scheme. This is notwithstanding the vast protection which the Act gives to employees under the scheme. The scant attention given to the pension trust under the Act may be due to the unique kind of pension trust created by the Act. For as we shall see, the trust created under the Act is diametrically different from the traditional pension trust under the common law.

Apart from the Act, the Guidelines for The Operations of Pension Fund Custodians released by the National Pension Commission⁷¹ states in paragraph 4.01 that, the “PFC shall open a trust account or accounts for the deposit of contributions with one or more banks. The PFC shall seek the commission’s prior approval for the appointment of a receiving bank, other than its parent”. This guideline mandates the PFC to open a trust account, which is an account opened by a trustee for the benefit of beneficiaries. This suggests that the PFC is a trustee. From the above provisions, it is the view of the present writer that the Pension Reform Act 2014 is unequivocally affirmative of a pension trust for the benefit of the employees.

As we have seen, the Act creates a trust for the protection of the pension fund. This trust, having been created by statute, is a statutory trust. However, this statutory trust remains inoperative till it is set in motion by the beneficiary, that is, the employee. Unlike the traditional trust which is “kick-started” by the settlor. The beneficiary to a pension trust has to choose his PFA as provided by the Act⁷². He, of course, must consider factors like; the investment choices the PFA offers, the number of changes in investment options it allows the beneficiary to make in a year, its network of branch offices, its regular provision of investment and retirement planning advisories, and its use of cutting - edge information and communication technology⁷³. After the PFA has been chosen, the PFA shall then choose a suitable trustee.

⁷⁰ The Pension Reform Act 2014 will herein after be referred to as “the Act”.

The use of Pension Trust under the common law in this essay is not to imply that there is a common law trust as opposed to equitable trust, but to describe the rules and nature of pension trust developed by the English Courts.

⁷¹ Publication on the official websites of the National Pension Commission. Accessed 1st of September, 2018 at <http://www.pencom.gov.ng>

⁷² Section 11(i) of the Act

⁷³ Odulana, F. O. (March 26, 2006). *How to choose your pension fund administrator*. Accessed on 14th of September, 2018 at <http://www.proshareng.com>

In the Pension trust under the Act, it is submitted that the PFA is the settlor, being the person who creates the trust in favour of the beneficiary. Under the Act, the PFC becomes a trustee by virtue of contract. The Act does not stipulate the contents of the contract between the PFA and the PFC but provides, and rightly in the writer's view, that a PFA shall not keep any pension fund or asset with a pension fund custodian in whom the PFA has any business interest, share or any relationship whatsoever. This will help to minimize collusion between the PFA and PFC to defraud the beneficiary. The Pencom guidelines⁷⁴, happily, provide some mandatory contents of the contract between the PFA and PFC. Most relevant to this part of this discourse is paragraph 8.4 and 8.41 of the guidelines for the operations of Pension Fund Administrators.

The Distinction between the Pension Trust Created by the Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2014 and the Pension Trust under the Common Law

The statutory trust created under the Nigeria Pension Reform Act 2014 is at variance with the pension trust under common law. The Pension Trust created by the Act is sui generis. It fundamentally departs from the classical pension trust developed by the English Court and is weaved around its own unique laws better suited to chart its peculiar waters. Thus, it will be no exaggeration to say that both kinds of pension trusts are worlds apart. The major differences between the trust under the Pension Reform Act 2014 and the common law pension trust are stated below.

1. The classical pension trust is based on the contract of employment and the terms of the trust deed. Thus, the employer has a lot of discretion as regards the operation of the trust. As the court observed in *Mettey Pension Trustees Ltd v Evans* [1991] 2 AIER 513 at 537⁷⁵ that: "The member's rights have contractual and commercial origins. They are derived from the contracts of employment of the members".

Under the Act, the above dictum will be wholly inapplicable as the pension trust is largely governed by statute, in this case, the Pension Reforms Act 2014 and Guidelines from Pencom. It is only supplemented by general principles of trust and the custodial contract between the PFA and PFC. The terms of the custodial contract are also governed by statute, though not absolutely. Thus, the much admired flexibility of the traditional trusts and consequently common law Pension trust has been eroded by the Act.

2. At the root of the difference between both kinds of trust is that under the common law pension trust, the employer is generally under no obligation to create a

⁷⁴ Guidelines for the operations of Pension Fund Administrators and Pension Fund Custodian.

⁷⁵ [1991] 2 AIER 513 at 537

pension scheme for the employees⁷⁶. The employers, however, usually offer a pension scheme which they initially solely-sponsored. They are therefore deemed to be the settlors of the scheme as they appoint the trustees and may terminate the scheme. As Moffat explains⁷⁷, “in classic trusts law, the employer is the settlor of the trust. As such, it may reserve certain conditions to itself when setting up the trust. In OPT terms, this equates to the retention of powers within the trust deed to, for example, give or refuse consent to increases in pensions in payment, or to wind up the scheme, or to modify the terms of the scheme”.

However, the case is completely different with the trust under the Act. As already shown, the PFAs are the settlors who vest the legal estate to the fund on the PFC by way of a custodial contract. They have the power to terminate the trust, subject to the Act or Pencom guidelines.

3. Another fundamental change in the traditional pension trust brought about by the Act is the diminution of the traditional powers of a trustee. Under both a classic trust and a classic pension trust, the trustee manages and invests the trust fund. As regards a pension fund, the trustee’s duty to invest the trust fund is unshaken⁷⁸. The trustees are entitled to delegate their responsibilities and be free from liability provided that they have made a reasonable selection of delegates and undertaken reasonable supervision of the delegate⁷⁹. Under the Act, however, the duties of investment, administration or management of the fund are vested exclusively in the PFA. The PFC’s primary duty is to have custody of the pension fund⁸⁰. As Fashola has rightly said: “The trust relationship is however distinct from the more usual type where the trustee actively manages the beneficiary’s assets and investments.... Hence, the role of the PFCs is passive; as “bare” “trustees, with PFAs maintaining the most active role in pension fund administration”⁸¹.

This obviously inexorably leads to a barrage of conflicts of interests⁸² which deepen the complexity of pension trusts. The Pension Reform Act 2014 obviates such complexities by giving the beneficiary of the scheme the latitude to choose their own PFA and

⁷⁶ Hudson, A. (August, 2005). *Equity and trust*. 4th ed. London: Routledge Cavandish.

⁷⁷ Graham, M. Op. cit. Pg. 670.

⁷⁸ Hudson, A. Op. cit. Pg. 985.

⁷⁹ Speight v. Grant [1883] UKHL 1

⁸⁰ Section 62 of the Act

⁸¹ Fashola, L. (June 21, 2013). *Safe-keeping and custody of Pension Assets: The Nigerian experience*, ESQ Legal Practice. Pg. 1

⁸² The English Court of Appeal considered the problem of trustees’ conflict of interest in. *Edge v. Pensions Ombudsman* [2000] ch. 602, CA

mandating PFAs to keep pension funds or assets with a pension fund custodian otherwise than one in whom the pension fund administrator has any business interest, share or any relationship whatsoever⁸³.

It is beyond dispute that for the creation of a valid express trust, the 3 certainties of intention, subject matter and objects must co-exist⁸⁴. The pension fund established under the Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2014 contemplates the creation of an express pension fund by the PFA in favour of the PFC. It is not in doubt that from the contractual relation between the PFA and PFC, the intention to create a trust is manifest. Also, the beneficiary of the trust stands out a mile, as the entire Act revolves around the protection of the beneficiary that is the employee. However, as regards the condition of certainty of the subject matter, the nature of the pension assets may, arguably, fall short. This will depend on whether the pension assets are regarded as fungible or non – fungible. This challenge of fungibility was rightly pointed out by D. Fashola⁸⁵. Assets are said to be fungible if they are capable of mutual substitution or capable of being substituted in place of another.

That is, if such assets are identical to each other and can be used to replace each other. According to Benjamin and Yates⁸⁶, if “the custodian aggregates the holdings in securities of a particular issue which it holds for its various clients into one comingled holding”, such assets will be fungible. Thus, if the PFFC aggregates, that is, mixes up in one account the pension assets of different beneficiaries, the assets will be fungible given that the pension assets are identical. The implication of this is that the pension assets will not be identifiable and, in turn, will fail for uncertainty of subject matter as in *Sprange v Barnard* [1789] 2 BROCC 585 where a trust was held void due to, among other things, lack of certainty of the subject matter.

However, in the words of D. Fashola⁸⁷, the Consolidated Rules of the Security and Exchange Commission requires custodians to refrain from comingling investor assets but are required to operate separate custody accounts in their records for each client, resulting in non – fungible arrangements⁸⁸. Hence, the fungibility of pension assets and,

⁸³ Section 77 (2) of the Act

⁸⁴ *Charti Commissioner for England and Wales v. Franjee* [2014] EWHC pg. 2507

⁸⁵ Fashola, D. (2013). *Safe-keeping and custody of pension assets: The Nigerian experience*. ESQ Legal Practice, June 21. Pg. 1.

⁸⁶ Benjamin, J. & Yates, M. (2002). *The law of global custody* 2nd ed., Butter Worths.

⁸⁷ Fashola, D., op. cit.

⁸⁸ [1789] 2 Bro CC 585

invariably, certainty of subject matter of pension matter is wholly dependent on the PFC abiding by the Rules. It is suggested by the present writer that this be made a clause in the custody contract between the PFA and PFC so that he can be subject to the equitable remedy of specific performance if he fails to keep separate accounts or the injunctive remedy to restrain him from comingling the accounts. As between the beneficiary and the PFC, the beneficiary's remedy of injunction under trust still subsists and he can put it to effective use against the PFC in the event of an imminent disobedience to the rules.

Given the numerous statutory protections of the contributory pension scheme, the continued importance of a trust to the scheme may be brought into question. As a pension trust under the Act forms the kernel of this work, it is expedient to justify the creation of trust by the Act.

Though the provisions of the Act protecting the beneficiary may seem adequate, they are, ironically, very much limited. Under the Act, the beneficiary has no direct relationship with the trustee. The Act, in fact, prohibits the beneficiary from dealing with the PFC with respect to the retirement savings account except through the PFA⁸⁹. With the introduction of trust under the Act, an instrument with which the beneficiary can bring personal actions against the PFC comes in sight. The beneficiary overcomes the hurdle of going through a third party and the PFC is held more accountable.

The Pension Fund Administrator (PFA)

The PFA is by far the most dominant party to the pension trust under the Act. Being the settlor and manager of the trust, the PFA is undoubtedly the dynamo around which the pension trust under the Act revolves. As at December 30th, 2018⁹⁰, the number of PFAs in Nigeria were twenty-one. The Act defines a PFA as:

*"anybody corporate licensed by the commission as a Pension Fund Administrator"*⁹¹

A person who intends to operate as a PFA must apply to the Commission for a licence in the prescribed form together with fees prescribed by the Commission⁹² and if the Commission is satisfied that the applicant meets the requirements set out in Section 60 of the Act, it may issue a licence to the applicant to operate as a PFA subject to such

⁸⁹ Section 11(8) of the Act

⁹⁰ List of licenced Pension Fund Administrators in Nigeria, 30th December, 2018. Accessed on 30/12/2018 at <http://www.pencom.gov.ng>.

⁹¹ Section 120 of the Act

⁹² *Ibid*, Section 58(1)

terms and conditions as the Commission may consider expedient and necessary in the circumstances⁹³. Section 60 of the Act states that an application for licence to operate as a PFA shall not be granted unless the applicant is a limited liability company incorporated under the Companies and Allied Matters Act whose object is to manage pension funds, has a minimum paid up share capital of such sum as may be prescribed, from time to time, by the Commission, satisfies the Commission that it has the professional capacity to manage pension funds and administer retirement benefits; has never been a manager or administrator of any fund which was mismanaged or has been in distress due to any of its subscribers, directors or officers; undertakes to the satisfaction of the Commission, that it shall not be engaged in any business other than the management of pension funds; and satisfies any additional requirement or condition as may be prescribed, from time to time, by the Commission⁹⁴. Any company and institution already engaged in the management of pension funds who have not been licensed by the Commission shall, at the commencement of the Act, compute and credit all contributions to the retirement savings account opened by them for each contributor including distributable income and transfer all pension funds and assets held by them to PFAs and PFCs as may be determined by the Commission⁹⁵.

The Legal Status of the PFA – Is the PFA a Trustee or an Agent?

It was earlier stated the PFA, being the one who creates the trust, is the settlor of the pension trust. But this is just one side of the coin, for it only describes the legal status of the PFA from one perspective. The other side of the coin, however, is the legal status of the PFA as between him and the employee when he is chosen by the employee to manage the pension fund. In accepting this important but demanding duty, what legal relationship has the PFA entered into? This question is important as it determines what remedies the employee can seek in court against the PFA. That a contract is at the basis of their relationship stands out a mile but the question as to what legal relationship is created by the instrument of contract persists. To this question only two answers stand a chance - the PFA is either a trustee who is saddled with the responsibility of managing the pension assets or is an agent charged with the task of acting on behalf of the employee.

The conclusion that the PFA is a trustee is irresistible because the duties of the PFA under the Act are very much that of the traditional trustee. The PFA has the duty to manage, administer and invest the pension assets as a trustee will normally do. The fiduciary

⁹³ Section 58(2) of the Act

⁹⁴ *Ibid*, Section 60(1)

⁹⁵ *Ibid*, Section 60(2) - (3)

duties of a trustee are also clearly spelt out in the Act as duties of the PFA. The PenCom Guidelines also provide that marketable securities shall be registered in the joint name of the PFC and PFA in the format, Abc PFC for Xyz PFA⁹⁶ and immovable property in the joint name of the PFC and PFA in the same format above⁹⁷. The above guidelines may be supportive of the contention that the PFA is a trustee as they suggest joint title or ownership with the PFC. However, the strong temptation to describe the PFA as a trustee notwithstanding, the present writer submits that this should not be done in haste as the argument that the PFA is a trustee is not without its defects.

Though it can be impliedly created, it is often constituted by agreement⁹⁸. Unlike a trust where the beneficiary can sue the trustee, as long as the principal in an agency relationship is disclosed, the agent is not liable⁹⁹. Another essential difference between them is that title to property or assets is generally not vested in the agent. This is obviously superfluous as the agent merely acts on behalf of the principal.

A close perusal of the Act with respect to a PFA shows that the PFA perfectly fits into the doctrine of agency. As has been established, there are three inextricable elements of agency. These are consent by the principal and agent, action by the agent on behalf of the principal and control by the principal. These three elements are patently present in the Act. It's also settled that an agent may be general or specific. While a general agent is given authority to act on behalf of the principal with respect to every kind of business for a particular purpose, a specific agent is limited to a specific function. An example of a general agent is a managing director who as an agent of the company acts on behalf of the company for every aspect of the company's business subject to the articles and memorandum of association of the company. The PFA has all the characteristics of a general agent who performs all forms of functions within the scope of the management of the assets.

In addition, there are ample provisions where the Act would have expressly stated that the PFA was a trustee as it did with the PFC. However, the Act repeatedly emphasized that the PFA was only a manager of the assets and was totally barred from holding the funds¹⁰⁰. Also, with the PFC acting as a custodian trustee it would be most unnecessary to make the PFA a trustee since the PFC holds the funds on trust to the exclusive order of

⁹⁶ Paragraph 4.04 of the National Pension Commissions Guidelines for the Operation of the PFCs

⁹⁷ *Ibid*, Paragraph 4.08

⁹⁸ *Achoru v. Decagon Investment Ltd & Anor* [2014] LPELR – 24143 (CA) pg. 16, paras. E – G.

⁹⁹ *New Age Beverage Co. Ltd. v. Aramide* [2014] LPELR 23266 (CA) Pg. 13-14, Paras. G – E.

¹⁰⁰ Section 77(i) of the Act

the PFA¹⁰¹. The PFA would after taking a decision give the PFC instructions to put the decision to effect.

The Pension Fund Custodian (the PFC):

As variously stated earlier in the work, the PFC is the trustee in the pension trust created under the Act. This is an indubitable fact. The aim of this part is to examine some peculiarities of this trustee created by the Act.

According to Leo, a corporate trustee “is a corporate entity that holds and manages the properties or the assets of the trust for the benefit of the institutions called lenders who have advanced credit and other facilities to the borrower”¹⁰². The above definition, though correct for the above writer’s purposes, is very restrictive. The definition envisages the corporate trustee created by the Investment and Securities Act¹⁰³ which contemplates that the corporate trustee will play roles such as representing the interest of all the lenders for whose benefit the trust is set up by a borrower; keeping the title of any collateral property so that the borrower does not deal with them without its consent, taking legal action against the borrower on behalf of the lenders etc¹⁰⁴. Thus, the corporate trustee created by the Pension Reform Act is outside its ambit.

A corporate trustee is generally regarded as a company which acts as a trustee. The trustee is “corporate” because it has been conferred with legal personality and is not subject to the frailties of life as is a human being. Thus it has perpetual succession, can enter into contracts and can sue and be sued. According to the Act, a PFC means a company incorporated under the Companies and Allied Matters Act that has been licensed by the Commission under the Act¹⁰⁵. Also, a person proposing to act as a PFC shall be a limited liability company incorporated under the CAMA¹⁰⁶ by a licensed financial institution with the sole object of keeping custody of pension fund and retirement benefits assets and must fulfil the following conditions: a minimum paid up capital of such sum that may be prescribed by the commission from time to time and is wholly owned by a licensed financial institution with net worth of a minimum of ₦25,000,000,000 or as may be prescribed from time to time. It must show that the parent company has issued a guarantee to the full sum and value of the cash float of pension

¹⁰¹ Section 62(d) of the Act

¹⁰² Okafor, L. (2010). *Leo on Cooperate Trust*, 1st ed. Lagos: Prestige Books 2010, pg. 24.

¹⁰³ The Investment and Security Act 2007

¹⁰⁴ Rule 205(i) – (iv) Rules and Regulation of the SEC

¹⁰⁵ Section 120 of the Act

¹⁰⁶ Company and Allied Matter Act

funds and assets held by the PFC Company, as may be determined by the commission, from time to time. It undertakes to hold the pension fund assets to the exclusive order of the PFA on trust and has never been a custodian of any fund which was mismanaged or has been in distress due to any default of the PFC¹⁰⁷.

The PFC as a Custodian Trustee

In addition to the PFC being a corporate trustee, the PFC is also a custodian trustee. That is, a custodian in whom the legal title is vested for the benefit of another. The Act leaves no doubt as to this. It provides that:

“From the commencement of this Act, pension funds and assets shall only be held by pension funds custodians licensed by the Commission under this Act”.

A custodian is a person, corporate or otherwise who is in possession of property or assets for the benefit of another. Custodians are usually banks and other companies. The idea of a custodian trustee is not novel to Nigerian Law. The Public Trustee Law established by several state laws empowered the Public Trustee to act as a custodian trustee¹⁰⁸. In particular, Section 6(1) of the Public Trustee Law of Lagos State empowers the Public Trustee to, if he thinks fit, subject to and in accordance with the provisions of the law and the regulations made thereunder, act as an ordinary trustee; act as a custodian trustee, or be appointed trustee by the court. It further states that where the Public Trustee is appointed to be custodian trustee of any trust, the trust property shall be transferred to the custodian trustee as if he was sole trustee, and for that purpose vesting orders may, where necessary, be made by the Court¹⁰⁹. Also, the custodian trustee shall have the custody of all securities and documents of title relating to the trust property¹¹⁰. A natural consequence of being a custodian is the duty to keep the assets safe.

The two major duties of the PFC are – the duty to hold the pension funds and the duty to keep the funds safe. This was extensively discussed under the last heading. Other duties of the PFC include the duties to: on behalf of the PFA, settle transactions and undertake activities relating to the administration of pension fund investments including the collection of dividends, bonus, rental income, commissions and related activities, report to the Commission on matters relating to the assets being held by it on behalf of any PFA at such intervals as may be determined, from time to time, by the Commission; undertake statistical analysis on the investments and returns on investments with respect

¹⁰⁷ Section 62 of the Pension Reform Act 2014

¹⁰⁸ Trust and Equity Law of Enugu State CAP 153, Revised Laws of Enugu State.

¹⁰⁹ Section 8(2a) of the Public Trustee Act CAP P27, Laws of Lagos State 2004

¹¹⁰ Section 8 (2d) of the Public Trustee Act CAP P27, Laws of Lagos State 2004

to pension funds in its custody and provide data and information to the PFA and the Commission and execute in favour of the PFA relevant proxy for the purpose of voting in relation to the investments. Finally, the Act also mandates the PFC not to utilize any pension fund or assets in its custody to meet its own financial obligation to any person whatsoever¹¹¹.

Similarly, there exist trust relationships in oil and gas practice especially under charitable trust. A pointer to this is the novel arrangement of the Petroleum Host Communities (PHC) Fund provided for in the Petroleum Industry Bill. The Bill has being held to be such that will reform the oil and gas industry not only for incumbent administration but for subsequent administrations to come. An example of such reform is the 'Petroleum Host Communities Fund' created in favour of oil producing states whereby oil companies shall donate certain monies for the improvement of the lives of people in those states. In essence by analogy, a trust is created specifically an express public trust (Charitable Trust), as the oil companies are settlors, the state is the trustee, while the people in the oil producing state are the beneficiaries.

Constructive Trust

The courts in Nigeria rarely consider constructive trust, rather cases bordering on possible constructive trust remedies are considered under the general scope of breach of contract consequently, damages are routinely awarded as fair remedy. Although, there are few case laws that exemplify the willingness of the court to develop the doctrine of constructive trust in Nigeria. For example, in *AG of the Federation v. AG of Abia State & Ors* [2002] 4 SCNJ¹¹², the Supreme Court held that, the federation account that is used to retain some federal revenues which are shared by all the states and the central government is held on constructive trusts by the Federal Government. The judgment implies that, the federal government cannot unilaterally manipulate the revenue, where it does so, it must account for the profits. This means that, the federal government cannot unjustly enrich itself at the expense of the states thereof.

By this token, the federal government has the obligation to ensure fair dealings with the said revenue. In another relatively new case of *First Bank Nigeria v. Ozokwere* [2013] 12 (pt 11) M.J.S.C 60 at 77-78¹¹³ the Nigerian Supreme Court recognized that unjust enrichment is a viable cause of action where the ingredients are plausible that may not only be bound

¹¹¹ Section 70 (2) of The Pension Reform Act 2014

¹¹² [2002] 4 SCNJ

¹¹³ [2013] 12 (pt 11) M.J.S.C 60 at 77-78

by the doctrines of tort and contract. In *Eboni Finance & Sec. v. Wole-Ojo Technical Services* [1996] 7 NWLR (pt. 461) 464 at 478¹¹⁴, the court held that, in a proven circumstance where a party unjustly enriches himself at the cost of another, the duplicitous party must be “made to disgorge it”. The court further explained *inter alia*:

“Therefore, in consonance with the principles enshrined in the restitution a remedy shall be available whenever the defendant is unjustly enriched at the expense of the Plaintiff.”

Even though the court did not specifically impose a constructive trust, it did acknowledge its relevance as a model of restitution. Nigerian courts appear to treat unjust enrichment cases within the broad scope of restitution as a guided remedy which streams from the doctrine of equity hence, reluctant to see such cases as of constructive trust. The basis for restitution is the proprietary interest which a claimant holds in the enrichment obtained by the trustee. The right to restitution is principally within the scope of law and equity.

Similarly, the family head or community head could be held to account for unjust benefits obtained by him through the reckless handling of the common property¹¹⁵. The position of a reckless community or family head that unjustly profit from a community property is that of constructive trustee even though it is not often made clear by the Nigerian courts.

In a similar vein, the preamble of Nigeria’s Land Use Act 1978 states as follows:

*“An act to vest all land comprised in the territory of each state (except land vested in the Federal Government or its agencies) solely in the Governor of the State, who would hold such land in trust for the people and would henceforth be responsible for allocation of land in all urban areas to individuals’ resident in the state and organizations for residential agricultural, commercial and other purposes while similar powers with respect to non-urban areas are conferred on local governments”*¹¹⁶.

Section 1 of the Act vests all land comprised in each state (except lands vested in the Federal Government for its agencies) solely in the hands of the governor of the state, to hold in trust for the people. By this provision, there exist statutory trusts on all lands thereof.

¹¹⁴ [1996] 7 NWLR (pt. 461) 464 at 478

¹¹⁵ *Bassey v. Coban* (1924) 5 NLR 92

¹¹⁶ Land Use Act 1978

From the construction of the preamble and section 1 of the Act, it implies that the governor of every state as trustee of the lands ought and should act reasonably in the administration of lands. Although, there are currently seems to be no authority to illustrate unjust enrichment of any governor resulting from reckless handling of lands, the Land Use Act appears to give room for the governors to be held accountable for misuse of trust powers over lands. Where such event arises, the possibility of the court to create constructive trust is foreseeable. This means that, the governors cannot unjustly enrich themselves or breach the duties confined within the scope of the Land Use Act¹¹⁷.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The concept of trust cannot be said to be alien to the Nigeria legal system prior to the partition of Africa and the subsequent colonization of Nigeria. The concept of family ownership of land in Nigeria served a purpose similar to that of trust, where the concept of individual ownership is a foreign one, rather, land belongs to the family and the head of family holds the family land for the use of the family members. The concept of trust under customary law is however different from that under the English law because while the trustee is regarded as the owner of the trust property, the head of family is not regarded as the owner of the family property, but rather as the caretaker¹¹⁸.

The Land Use Act also embodied the concept of trust by vesting the control and management of land in each State of the federation in the Governors to be held in trust and administered for the use and common benefit of all Nigerians.

The very nature of a trust had been explored and in doing so, a number of key features relating to it had been examined. In particular, the respective positions of the trustee and beneficiaries under a trust and the nature of their interests. The basic feature of the trust is that it facilitates the fragmentation of ownership of property, thereby creating duality of rights in respect of the same thing. Although the legal title to the trust property is vested in the trustee, the equitable interest belongs to the beneficiary. The importance of the trust in English law cannot be under- estimated and it is for this precise reason that Maitland was to comment that it is one of the greatest achievements of English¹¹⁹.

¹¹⁷ Land Use Act 1978

¹¹⁸ *Ibid*

¹¹⁹ Moutland, F. W. (1936). *Equity* (2nd ed.). P. 23.

It had been shown that a constructive trust is not a voluntary creation, but a mechanism by benefit of which precise property is vested in a trustee on trust for ascertainable beneficiaries. It was also shown that constructive trust may arise due to a breach of fiduciary obligations. However, the duty of a constructive trustee is less arduous than those of the express trustees in the sense that, they do not have to comply wholly on the usual duty of care. However, failure to comply with the terms of the constructive trust may result in stricter sanctions by the court. The only way to reach the contrary conclusion would be to say that this is the technique of equity: to subject trustees, even unwilling ones, to the fiduciary standard, so as to generate the corresponding liabilities. That however, would be using the fiduciary relationship in a wholly instrumental way”.

In view of the emphasized basic principles of constructive trust, the conclusion is that, the settings in which constructive trusts have been adjudicated by the courts in England and elsewhere, to exist are yet to be fully explored in Nigeria. Nigerian courts are therefore, urged to explore the constructive trust as a valuable remedy for breach of fiduciary duties especially where the recovery of a trust property is still in the possession of the defendant. Alternatively, to aid in the tracing of the proceeds where there are evidences to show that the constructive trustees have disposed of the trust property.

Recommendations

There still exists gap between the concept of trust as practice in England compare to what we have here in Nigeria. Trust as a foreign concept of law, and like other received English laws have failed to yield much result in Nigeria due to the fact that those laws are built on English ideals which are not compactable with our own ideals, culture, customs and traditions. In a heterogeneous society like Nigeria, customs, traditions, religious beliefs and to some extent disagreement between the beneficiaries of a trust are some of the causes of the problems associated with trusteeship. To this end, attempt should be made to find a balance between these onerous contending factors and harmonize them in order to unified and ideal trust law in Nigeria.

The trust concept in the Nigerian Pension Reform Act 2014 can be expounded through detailed provisions in the Act spelling out the operation and ambit of the trust. It is interestingly so that Section 115(1) of the Act empowers the National Commission to make regulations, rules or guidelines as it deems necessary or expedient for giving full effect to the provisions of the Act. The Act do not really need any amendment; it will suffice if the Pension Commission should make guidelines for the pension trust in the Act.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ¹ [1991] 5 NWLR (Pt. 190) p. 130
² Nwabueze, B. O. (1973). *Nigeria land law*. Nwamife Publishers: Enugu. p.7.
³ See Black's Law Dictionary (5th ed.). St. Paul Mim. West Publishing Co. p.997.
⁴ Nwabueze, B. O. op.cit.
⁵ [1921] C399 at 404
⁶ See *Amodu Tijani v Secretary Southern Province* [1921] 3 NLR 24.

⁷ Ibid.
⁸ See *Amodu Tijani v. Secretary Southern Province (supra)*.
⁹ Yakubu, M. G. (1981). *Nigerian land law*. Macmillan.
¹⁰ Ibid.
¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Yakubu, M. G. op.cit.
¹³ Niki Tobi (1992). *Cases and materials on land law*.
¹⁴ Yakubu, M. G. (1981). *Nigerian land law*. Macmillan. p.59-60.
¹⁵ Ibid.
¹⁶ Allot, *Essays in African Law*. p.70.
¹⁷ Yakubu, M. G. (1981). *Nigerian land law*. Macmillan. p.60.
¹⁸ Ibid.
¹⁹ Political Memoranda No. 10, Para. 11.
²⁰ [1921] 3 NLR 24
²¹ Ibid
²² Ibid
²³ *Ogunmefun v Ogunmefun* [1961] 10 NLR 82
²⁴ *Adesoye v. Taiwo* [1956] 1 FSC 84
²⁵ *Adagun v. Fagbola* [1943] 11 NLR 110
²⁶ *Bassey v. Cobham* [1974] 5 NLR 90
²⁷ *Kosoko v. Kosoko* [1975] 13 NLR 131
²⁸ Ibid
²⁹ Ibid
³⁰ [1941] 6 N.L.R 26 at p.27
³¹ Elias, T. O. (1971). *Nigerian land law*. Sweet and Maxwell: London. p.105.
³² [1962] LLR 32
³³ James, R. W. (1973). *Modern law of Nigeria*. University of Ife Press: Ile-Ife, Nigeria.
³⁴ *Taiwo v. Sarumi* [1913] 2 NLR 84
³⁵ *Adigun v. Fagbola* [1943] 11 NLR 100
³⁶ *Lewis v. Bankole* [1909] 1 NLR 82
³⁷ Yakubu, M. G. (1981). *Nigerian land law*. Macmillan
³⁸ [1924] 5 N.L.R 90
³⁹ [1974] 5 NLR 90
⁴⁰ *Adegbite v. Lawal* [1948] 12 WACA 398
⁴¹ *Coker v. Coker* [1938] 14 NLR 83
⁴² Ibid.
⁴³ James, R. W. (Supra) at p. 88.
⁴⁴ Ibid.

- ⁴⁵ Yakubu, M. G. (1981). *Nigerian land law*. Macmillan.
- ⁴⁶ Amodu Tijani v Secretary Southern Province [1921] 3 NLR 24.
- ⁴⁷ Nwabueze, B. O. (1973). *Nigeria land law* (supra).
- ⁴⁸ Ife v. Chief Adedire
- ⁴⁹ Ajibola v. Ajibola [1947] 18 NLR 125.
- ⁵⁰ [1977] WLR 521
- ⁵¹ [1865] L.R. 1 Ch. App. 25
- ⁵² [1798] 3 Ves 696 per Arden M.R
- ⁵³ *Ibid* Law of Property Act 1925
- ⁵⁴ Section 9 Wills Act 1837
- ⁵⁵ Section 2, Infant Act CAP. 49 Laws of Western Region
- ⁵⁶ [2001] 9 N.W.L.R. (Part 718) p. 429
- ⁵⁷ Settled Act 1882
- ⁵⁸ [1978] 1 W.L.R. 770
- ⁵⁹ Section 180, Property and Conveyance Law CAP. 100 Laws of Western Region of Nigeria
- ⁶⁰ Section 38(i) CAMA 2004
- ⁶¹ Security and Exchange Commission Rules and Regulations 2002, 2003, 2005 for its regulation on collective investment schemes through trust, particularly unit trusts.
- ⁶² Moffat, G. (2005). *Trusts Law, Text and Materials*. 4th ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press).
- ⁶³ Kasim v. NNPC [2013] 10 NWLR (Pt 1361) pg. 69, para C-D.
- ⁶⁴ Momodu v. National Union of Local Government Employees [1994] 8 NWLR (pt 362) pg. 336.
- ⁶⁵ Moffat, G. (2005). *Trusts Law, Text and Materials*. 4th ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press). Pg. 670.
- ⁶⁶ Moffat, G., op. cit. pg. 645
- ⁶⁷ Section 3(i) of the Pension Reform Act 2014
- ⁶⁸ *Ibid* Section 11(i)
- ⁶⁹ *Ibid* Section 120
- ⁷⁰ Section 120 of the Pension Reform Act 2014
- ⁷¹ *Ibid* Section 7(i)(a)-(c)
- ⁷² Section 11(i) of the Act
- ⁷³ Odulana, F. O. (March 26, 2006). *How to choose your pension fund administrator*. Accessed on 14th of September, 2018 at <http://www.proshareng.com>
- ⁷⁴ Guidelines for the operations of Pension Fund Administrators and Pension Fund Custodian.
- ⁷⁵ [1991] 2 AIIER 513 at 537
- ⁷⁶ Hudson, A. (August, 2005). *Equity and trust*. 4th ed. London: Routledge Cavandish.
- ⁷⁷ Graham, M. Op. cit. Pg. 670.
- ⁷⁸ Hudson, A. Op. cit. Pg. 985.
- ⁷⁹ Speight v. Grant [1883] UKHL 1
- ⁸⁰ Section 62 of the Act
- ⁸¹ Fashola, L. (June 21, 2013). *Safe-keeping and custody of Pension Assets: The Nigerian experience*, ESQ Legal Practice. Pg. 1
- ⁸² The English Court of Appeal considered the problem of trustees' conflict of interest in. *Edge v. Pensions Ombudsman* [2000] ch. 602, CA
- ⁸³ Section 77 (2) of the Act
- ⁸⁴ *Charti Commissioner for England and Wales v. Franjee* [2014] EWHC pg. 2507
- ⁸⁵ Fashola, D. (2013). *Safe-keeping and custody of pension assets: The Nigerian experience*. ESQ Legal Practice, June 21. Pg. 1.
- ⁸⁷ Benjamin, J. & Yates, M. (2002). *The law of global custody* 2nd ed., Butter Worths.
- ⁸⁸ Fashola, D., op. cit.
- ⁸⁹ [1789] 2 Bro CC 585

- ⁹⁰ Section 11(8) of the Act
- ⁹¹ List of licenced Pension Fund Administrators in Nigeria, 30th December, 2018. Accessed on 30/12/2018 at <http://www.pencom.gov.ng>.
- ⁹² Section 120 of the Act
- ⁹³ *Ibid*, Section 58(1)
- ⁹⁴ Section 58(2) of the Act
- ⁹⁵ *Ibid*, Section 60(1)
- ⁹⁶ *Ibid*, Section 60(2) - (3)
- ⁹⁷ Paragraph 4.04 of the National Pension Commissions Guidelines for the Operation of the PFCs
- ⁹⁸ *Ibid*, Paragraph 4.08
- ⁹⁹ *Achoru v. Decagon Investment Ltd & Anor* [2014] LPELR – 24143 (CA) pg. 16, paras. E – G.
- ¹⁰⁰ *New Age Beverage Co. Ltd. v. Aramide* [2014] LPELR 23266 (CA) Pg. 13-14, Paras. G – E.
- ¹⁰¹ Section 77(i) of the Act
- ¹⁰² Section 62(d) of the Act
- ¹⁰³ Okafor, L. (2010). *Leo on Cooperate Trust*, 1st ed. Lagos: Prestige Books 2010, pg. 24.
- ¹⁰⁴ The Investment and Security Act 2007
- ¹⁰⁵ Rule 205(i) – (iv) Rules and Regulation of the SEC
- ¹⁰⁶ Section 120 of the Act
- ¹⁰⁷ Company and Allied Matter Act
- ¹⁰⁸ Section 62 of the Pension Reform Act 2014
- ¹⁰⁹ Trust and Equity Law of Enugu State CAP 153, Revised Laws of Enugu State.
- ¹¹⁰ Section 8(2a) of the Public Trustee Act CAP P27, Laws of Lagos State 2004
- ¹¹¹ Section 8 (2d) of the Public Trustee Act CAP P27, Laws of Lagos State 2004
- ¹¹² Section 70 (2) of The Pension Reform Act 2014
- ¹¹³ [2002] 4 SCNJ
- ¹¹⁴ [2013] 12 (pt 11) M.J.S.C 60 at 77-78
- ¹¹⁵ [1996] 7 NWLR (pt. 461) 464 at 478
- ¹¹⁶ *Bassey v. Coban* (1924) 5 NLR 92
- ¹¹⁷ Land Use Act 1978
- ¹¹⁸ Land Use Act 1978
- ¹¹⁹ Moutland, F. W. (1936). *Equity* (2nd ed.). P. 23.